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A complete set of minimal components for the asymmetric cell division program.

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Gene expression in the human cell can be described through a set of expression programs comprised of a collection of representative gene products. We recently defined the senescence program in human cells. Here we describe a minimal set of components for the asymmetric cell division program. The genes include POF1A/B, APH1A/B, MON1A/B, and a set of characteristic kinesin family KIF genes that describe differences in completion of the cell cycle and production of the daughter cell that define asymmetric cell division.